

a)

$$\%maternal = \frac{[Cm]}{[Cm + Cuc]}$$

$$\%cord = \frac{[Cuc]}{[Cm + Cuc]}$$

b)

a)

$$\%maternal = \frac{[Cm]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$

$$\%cord = \frac{[Cuc]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$

$$\%placenta = \frac{[Cp]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$

b)

%Average percentage distribution between maternal -fetal unit (ng/g lipid)

$$\%mother = \frac{[Cm]}{[Cm + Cuc]}$$

$$\%newborn = \frac{[Cuc]}{[Cm + Cuc]}$$

a)

b)

$$\%maternal = \frac{[Cm]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$

$$\%cord = \frac{[Cuc]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$

$$\%placenta = \frac{[Cp]}{[Cm + Cuc + Cp]}$$